

IMPROVEMENT OF THE INVESTIGATION OF CRIMES RELATED TO KNOWINGLY FALSE TESTIMONY BY A WITNESS OR VICTIM

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Annotation. *This article analyzes current problems in investigating crimes related to knowingly false testimony given by witnesses or victims. Particular attention is paid to gaps and inconsistencies in criminal procedural legislation, as well as logical contradictions arising in law enforcement practice. The issues of warning witnesses and victims about criminal liability during investigative actions are substantiated. The author proposes specific recommendations aimed at improving legislation and enhancing the effectiveness of investigative practice.*

Key words: *witness, victim, false testimony, criminal liability, investigative practice, criminal procedure law, legal gaps.*

1. INTRODUCTION

It is widely recognized that society and the social relations existing within it are in a constant state of development. Modern life is characterized by unprecedented rates of change, resulting in the emergence of new forms of social interaction. Simultaneously, new types of criminal conduct continue to evolve, while the methods employed in the commission of crimes become increasingly sophisticated and diverse. Consequently, legislation must be continuously improved in accordance with the pace of social development. Otherwise, the principles of justice and legal certainty within society may be undermined. As Immanuel Kant observed, laws and the organization of society should evolve in accordance with the development of human consciousness [1].

From this perspective, comprehensive reforms have been consistently implemented in Uzbekistan's judicial and legal system alongside reforms in other sectors of public administration. The guiding principle of these reforms is reflected in the idea of "For Human Dignity and People's Well-Being," which has become the cornerstone of state policy [2].

In particular, Presidential Decree No. PF-4850 of 21 October 2016 "On Measures for Further Reforming the Judicial and Legal System and Strengthening Guarantees for the Reliable Protection of Citizens' Rights and Freedoms" [3], Presidential Decree No. PF-5268 of 30 November 2017 "On Additional Measures to Strengthen Guarantees of Citizens' Rights and Freedoms in Judicial and Investigative Activities" [4], Presidential Decree No. PF-6041 of 10 August 2020 "On Measures to Further Strengthen Guarantees for the Protection of Individual Rights and Freedoms in Judicial and Investigative Activities" [5], and Presidential Resolution No. PQ-3723 of 14 May 2018 "On Measures for the Radical Improvement of the System of Criminal and Criminal Procedural Legislation" [6] serve as vivid examples of these reforms.

The systematic and consistent reforms carried out during the years of independence are particularly significant because they have primarily been aimed at strengthening the principles of humanism within criminal and criminal procedural legislation [7].

At the same time, legal reform should not remain merely a formal process. Achieving the intended objectives requires continuous analysis of legislation, timely elimination of identified deficiencies, and effective filling of existing legal gaps.

Unless achievements and shortcomings are assessed objectively, sustainable progress cannot be achieved. As emphasized by President Shavkat Mirziyoyev, unresolved problems cannot be addressed by external actors but must be solved through internal legal and institutional improvement [8].

Furthermore, President Shavkat Mirziyoyev has stressed the necessity of continuing efforts aimed at the modernization and liberalization of criminal legislation. According to him, the Criminal Code and the Criminal Procedure Code were adopted nearly twenty-five years ago, and the significant changes that have occurred in social relations, lifestyles, legal awareness, and public consciousness have rendered many of their provisions inconsistent with contemporary realities [9].

President Mirziyoyev has also emphasized that the implementation of constitutional principles requires further efforts aimed at improving living standards, strengthening the protection of human rights, and ensuring that citizens experience the practical results of reforms in their daily lives rather than merely in the future [10].

In order to ensure logical consistency within this study, it is necessary, before addressing the improvement of investigations concerning knowingly false testimony by witnesses or victims, to examine the practical and theoretical problems currently encountered in law enforcement practice. The existence of such problems itself demonstrates the need for legislative and procedural improvement.

In our view, a comprehensive analysis should first identify the existing shortcomings and only thereafter propose appropriate solutions. Accordingly, the problems associated with investigating crimes involving knowingly false testimony by witnesses or victims may be divided into two categories:

Practical problems arising in investigative and judicial practice;

Theoretical problems arising from gaps, ambiguities, and contradictions in criminal procedural legislation and subordinate normative legal acts.

Practical problems include difficulties encountered in detecting and proving crimes involving knowingly false testimony, preparing and conducting investigative actions, documenting their results, and evaluating evidentiary materials. These problems are further aggravated by the fact that many investigators and inquiry officers currently serving in law enforcement agencies possess limited professional experience, while the number of highly qualified specialists capable of providing effective mentorship remains insufficient.

Theoretical problems primarily concern legal gaps, ambiguities, and contradictions within legislative and subordinate regulatory acts governing the investigation of crimes involving knowingly false testimony by witnesses and victims.

Taking the foregoing into consideration, special attention should be devoted to the current state of interrogation as an investigative action and to the shortcomings revealed through the analysis of judicial and investigative practice. These issues require comprehensive discussion together with the development of legislative proposals aimed at eliminating the identified deficiencies and improving the effectiveness of criminal investigations involving knowingly false testimony.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

The issue of knowingly false testimony has traditionally occupied an important place in criminal law and criminal procedure scholarship. The reliability of witness and victim testimony constitutes one of the fundamental guarantees of legality, objectivity, and fairness in criminal

proceedings. Consequently, legislators and legal scholars have consistently sought effective mechanisms to prevent, detect, and punish false testimony.

In the legal doctrine of Uzbekistan, various aspects of criminal procedural guarantees, evidentiary law, and the protection of participants in criminal proceedings have been examined by numerous scholars. Significant contributions to the development of theoretical approaches concerning procedural safeguards and evidentiary reliability have been made by M. Kh. Rustambayev, B. B. Murodov, and other specialists in criminal law and criminal procedure.

According to Rustambayev, knowingly false testimony directly undermines the administration of justice and creates substantial obstacles to the establishment of objective truth in criminal proceedings [11]. Criminal liability for false testimony therefore serves as an important legal instrument for protecting the integrity of investigative and judicial activities.

Murodov, while examining procedural guarantees and the institution of termination of criminal proceedings, emphasizes the necessity of maintaining an appropriate balance between the rights of participants in criminal proceedings and the interests of justice [7]. His research indirectly addresses issues concerning the procedural status of witnesses and victims and the importance of strengthening procedural safeguards.

Foreign legal scholarship likewise devotes considerable attention to the phenomenon of false testimony. Researchers generally acknowledge that testimonial evidence is particularly vulnerable to subjective distortions resulting from memory limitations, psychological pressure, personal interests, emotional involvement, and external influence. Consequently, modern criminal justice systems increasingly rely upon procedural safeguards designed both to enhance the reliability of testimonial evidence and to protect fundamental human rights.

Comparative legal studies demonstrate that numerous jurisdictions have incorporated constitutional and procedural guarantees aimed at preventing compelled self-incrimination and protecting close relatives of suspects and accused persons. Such guarantees are particularly evident in the legal systems of the Russian Federation and the United States.

Article 51 of the Constitution of the Russian Federation establishes that no person may be compelled to testify against himself, herself, a spouse, or close relatives as defined by federal law [14]. Similarly, the Fifth Amendment to the Constitution of the United States protects individuals against compelled self-incrimination and constitutes one of the fundamental principles of criminal justice [15].

An analysis of the criminal procedural legislation of Kazakhstan and Turkmenistan demonstrates that these legal systems contain more detailed provisions governing the procedural status of witnesses and victims during confrontation proceedings and identification procedures [18; 19]. In particular, these jurisdictions expressly require that witnesses and victims be warned of criminal liability for refusing to testify and for knowingly providing false testimony during various investigative actions involving testimonial evidence.

Despite the substantial body of scholarship devoted to criminal procedure and evidentiary law, the specific problems associated with investigating crimes involving knowingly false testimony by witnesses and victims remain insufficiently studied within the legal literature of Uzbekistan. In particular, issues relating to contradictory procedural statuses, the participation of close relatives, and the warning of criminal liability during various investigative actions require further scientific examination.

Therefore, the present study seeks to contribute to the existing body of knowledge by identifying legislative gaps, analyzing practical difficulties encountered by investigative

authorities, examining foreign legal experience, and developing proposals aimed at improving the criminal procedural legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

3. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The present research is based on a combination of general scientific and special legal research methods.

The dialectical method was employed to examine the evolution of criminal procedural regulation concerning witness and victim testimony and to identify the relationship between legislative provisions and law enforcement practice.

The formal legal method was used to analyze and interpret the provisions of the Criminal Code and Criminal Procedure Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan regulating criminal liability for knowingly false testimony and procedural guarantees applicable to witnesses and victims [12; 16].

A comparative legal method was applied to examine the legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan alongside the criminal procedural legislation of Kazakhstan, Turkmenistan, the Russian Federation, and the United States [14; 15; 18; 19]. This comparative analysis made it possible to identify similarities, differences, and potential directions for legislative improvement.

The method of legal analysis and synthesis was utilized to examine judicial and investigative practice, identify contradictions and legal gaps, and formulate scientifically grounded recommendations aimed at improving criminal procedural legislation.

The empirical basis of the research consists of materials from investigative and judicial practice relating to the application of criminal liability for knowingly false testimony, as well as practical situations encountered during inquiry and preliminary investigation proceedings.

The study further relied upon the analysis of legislative acts, presidential decrees, constitutional provisions, scientific publications, doctrinal sources, and criminal case materials relevant to the subject matter [3–6].

The combination of doctrinal, comparative, analytical, and practical approaches ensured the comprehensiveness of the research and facilitated the development of proposals aimed at improving both criminal procedural legislation and law enforcement practice concerning crimes involving knowingly false testimony by witnesses and victims.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1. Practical and Theoretical Problems in the Investigation of Crimes Involving Knowingly False Testimony

The analysis conducted within the framework of this research demonstrates that the investigation of crimes involving knowingly false testimony by witnesses and victims is accompanied by a number of practical and theoretical difficulties that negatively affect the effectiveness of criminal proceedings.

The practical problems primarily concern the detection, documentation, and proof of knowingly false testimony, as well as the organization and conduct of investigative actions.

These difficulties are often exacerbated by insufficient professional experience among investigators and inquiry officers, the shortage of qualified mentors, and inconsistencies in the application of procedural legislation.

Theoretical problems, in turn, arise from legislative gaps, ambiguous legal provisions, and contradictions within criminal procedural legislation governing the procedural status of witnesses and victims and the scope of criminal liability for knowingly false testimony.

The analysis of investigative and judicial practice indicates that many of these problems

originate from the absence of clear legislative regulation concerning situations frequently encountered during criminal proceedings.

4.2. Contradictions Related to the Application of Article 117 of the Criminal Procedure Code

One of the most significant issues concerns the application of Article 117 of the Criminal Procedure Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Article 117(1) provides that after establishing the identity of a witness or victim and explaining his or her procedural rights and obligations, the person shall be warned of criminal liability for refusing to testify and for knowingly providing false testimony, and such warning shall be recorded in the interrogation report or court record [12].

However, investigative practice demonstrates the existence of situations in which the application of this provision produces logical inconsistencies.

Particularly illustrative are criminal cases involving bodily injuries where both participants inflict injuries upon one another. In practice, an individual who initially suffers violence frequently responds with retaliatory actions instead of immediately contacting law enforcement authorities or seeking medical assistance.

Under such circumstances, both participants may simultaneously acquire dual procedural status within the same criminal proceeding. Each individual may be recognized both as a victim and as a suspect.

This situation gives rise to a significant procedural contradiction. When questioned as suspects, individuals are not warned of criminal liability for refusing to testify or for knowingly providing false testimony because suspects possess the right to remain silent and the right to defense [12]. However, when questioned as victims within the same criminal case, those same individuals are warned of criminal liability for refusing to testify and for knowingly providing false testimony.

Such a distinction raises serious concerns regarding the internal consistency of criminal procedural legislation.

According to criminal law doctrine, the offence of knowingly providing false testimony is considered completed from the moment a witness or victim signs the interrogation report following the conclusion of questioning [11]. At the same time, a suspect may lawfully refuse to testify or even provide inaccurate information in the exercise of the right to defense without incurring criminal liability.

The contradiction becomes particularly evident where an individual initially participates in criminal proceedings as a witness or victim and subsequently acquires the procedural status of suspect or accused person in connection with the same incident. In such situations, even if it is established that the person knowingly provided false testimony while acting as a witness or victim, imposing criminal liability under Article 238 of the Criminal Code becomes problematic due to the procedural guarantees afforded to suspects and accused persons [16].

Consequently, the current legislative framework creates uncertainty concerning the legal consequences of knowingly false testimony provided under such circumstances.

4.3. Problems Arising in Cases Involving Multiple Offenders

Another significant issue emerges during the investigation of crimes committed by groups of individuals acting in concert.

Where one of several suspects absconds and evades investigation, the proceedings relating to that individual are separated into a distinct criminal case pursuant to Article 332 of the

Criminal Procedure Code [12]. The person may subsequently be declared an accused in absentia, subjected to a preventive measure, placed on a wanted list, and the preliminary investigation may be suspended pursuant to Article 364 of the Criminal Procedure Code.

Meanwhile, the proceedings concerning the remaining participants continue and are referred to court for adjudication. Following judicial consideration, a conviction and sentence may be imposed.

If the fugitive is later apprehended, the suspended investigation is resumed pursuant to Article 371 of the Criminal Procedure Code [12]. During the renewed investigation, contradictions may arise between the testimony of the convicted person serving a sentence and that of the newly apprehended accused.

In practice, investigators frequently summon the convicted person as a witness, conduct an interrogation, and subsequently organize a confrontation between the convicted individual and the newly apprehended accused.

The difficulty lies in the fact that the convicted person is warned of criminal liability for refusing to testify and for knowingly providing false testimony despite having already been convicted in relation to the same criminal act.

Such practice appears inconsistent with the constitutional principle prohibiting repeated prosecution or punishment for the same offence [13]. Consequently, questions arise concerning the compatibility of existing procedural practice with the principles of fairness, legal certainty, and protection against double jeopardy.

4.4. Problems Related to the Participation of Close Relatives

Additional difficulties arise in connection with the participation of close relatives of suspects, accused persons, and defendants.

Article 116 of the Criminal Procedure Code provides that close relatives may be questioned concerning circumstances relating to a suspect or accused person only with their consent [12]. At the same time, Article 117(2) establishes that close relatives shall not be warned of liability for refusing to testify.

A systematic interpretation of these provisions leads to the conclusion that where close relatives voluntarily agree to testify, they should be warned of criminal liability for knowingly providing false testimony under Articles 238 and 240 of the Criminal Code [16].

Nevertheless, the analysis of investigative practice demonstrates that such warnings are frequently omitted. Furthermore, case materials reveal numerous instances in which close relatives are questioned without obtaining their explicit consent, despite the direct requirement established by law.

These shortcomings indicate the existence of legislative ambiguities and deficiencies in procedural regulation, which contribute to inconsistent law enforcement practice and may negatively affect the protection of procedural rights.

4.5. Comparative Legal Analysis and Foreign Experience

A comparative analysis of foreign criminal procedural legislation demonstrates that a number of jurisdictions have established more comprehensive procedural safeguards concerning the participation of witnesses and victims in investigative activities involving testimonial evidence.

Particularly noteworthy is the legislation of the Russian Federation, where the privilege against self-incrimination has been elevated to the level of a constitutional principle. Article 51(1) of the Constitution of the Russian Federation explicitly provides that no person shall be

compelled to testify against himself, herself, a spouse, or close relatives as determined by federal law [14].

Similarly, the Fifth Amendment to the Constitution of the United States guarantees protection against compelled self-incrimination and has become one of the fundamental constitutional safeguards within the American criminal justice system [15].

These constitutional provisions establish a clear legal framework protecting individuals from coercive procedural practices and ensuring the voluntary nature of testimony.

The criminal procedural legislation of Kazakhstan and Turkmenistan also contains provisions that are more detailed than the corresponding norms currently found in the Criminal Procedure Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Article 218 of the Criminal Procedure Code of the Republic of Kazakhstan requires that witnesses and victims participating in confrontation proceedings be warned of criminal liability for refusing to testify and for knowingly providing false testimony [18]. Likewise, Article 230 of the same Code establishes similar requirements for identification procedures.

Comparable provisions are contained in the Criminal Procedure Code of Turkmenistan. Article 258 requires the warning of witnesses and victims during confrontation proceedings, while Article 268 establishes identical requirements during identification procedures [19].

The existence of these provisions significantly reduces the possibility of contradictory interpretations and contributes to greater uniformity in law enforcement practice.

The comparative analysis therefore demonstrates that the legislation of Uzbekistan would benefit from the incorporation of more detailed procedural safeguards concerning warnings of criminal liability during investigative actions involving testimonial evidence.

4.6. Legislative Reform Proposals

The analysis conducted in this study demonstrates the necessity of introducing amendments to the Criminal Procedure Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

First, Article 117 should be supplemented by provisions clarifying the procedural status of close relatives who voluntarily agree to testify as witnesses or victims. Such individuals should be warned of criminal liability for knowingly providing false testimony while retaining their right to refuse testimony concerning close family members.

Second, the legislation should expressly regulate situations in which a person simultaneously acquires the procedural status of victim and suspect or accused person within the same criminal proceeding. Under such circumstances, the application of criminal liability for knowingly false testimony requires a differentiated procedural approach.

Third, convicted or acquitted persons questioned regarding separated criminal proceedings arising from the same criminal act should not be warned of criminal liability for refusing to testify or for knowingly providing false testimony, since such warnings may conflict with constitutional guarantees and principles of criminal justice.

Fourth, Articles 123 and 131 of the Criminal Procedure Code should be amended in order to require that witnesses and victims participating in confrontation proceedings and identification procedures be warned of criminal liability for refusing to testify and for knowingly providing false testimony.

Such amendments would contribute to the elimination of legislative ambiguities and strengthen the consistency of law enforcement practice.

5. SCIENTIFIC NOVELTY

The scientific novelty of the present research consists of the following:

Identification of previously insufficiently studied procedural contradictions arising where an individual simultaneously acquires the status of victim and suspect or accused person within the same criminal proceeding;

Comprehensive analysis of legal uncertainties concerning the participation of convicted persons and close relatives in investigative activities involving testimonial evidence;

Substantiation of the necessity of introducing a differentiated procedural approach regarding warnings of criminal liability for knowingly false testimony;

Comparative legal analysis of the legislation of Uzbekistan, Kazakhstan, Turkmenistan, the Russian Federation, and the United States concerning procedural safeguards applicable to witnesses and victims;

Development of proposals aimed at improving Articles 117, 123, and 131 of the Criminal Procedure Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan;

Formulation of recommendations intended to ensure a uniform interpretation and application of criminal procedural legislation

6. PRACTICAL SIGNIFICANCE

The practical significance of the research lies in the possibility of applying the proposed legislative amendments in the process of further improving the criminal procedural legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

The recommendations developed in this study may contribute to:

eliminating legal ambiguities and contradictions in criminal procedural legislation;

strengthening procedural guarantees for participants in criminal proceedings;

improving the effectiveness of investigations involving knowingly false testimony by witnesses and victims;

ensuring greater consistency and predictability in investigative and judicial practice;

enhancing the professional training of investigators, inquiry officers, prosecutors, and judges.

Furthermore, the findings of this research may be utilized in legal education, professional development programs, and future academic studies devoted to criminal procedure and evidentiary law.

7. CONCLUSION

The conducted research demonstrates that the investigation of crimes involving knowingly false testimony by witnesses and victims remains one of the most complex areas of criminal procedure and investigative practice.

The analysis of current legislation and law enforcement practice revealed the existence of significant legal gaps, inconsistencies, and procedural contradictions affecting the effectiveness of criminal investigations. Particular difficulties arise in determining the procedural status of participants who simultaneously possess several procedural capacities, regulating the testimony of close relatives, and establishing uniform rules concerning warnings of criminal liability during investigative actions involving testimonial evidence.

The study established that the current provisions of the Criminal Procedure Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan do not fully regulate all procedural situations encountered in practice. As a result, investigators are often compelled to rely on discretionary interpretations, which may negatively affect the consistency, predictability, and fairness of criminal proceedings.

The comparative legal analysis conducted within the framework of this research demonstrated that foreign legal systems have developed more comprehensive procedural

safeguards designed to regulate the participation of witnesses and victims in criminal proceedings and to ensure the reliability of testimonial evidence. Certain elements of these approaches may be effectively incorporated into the legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Based on the identified shortcomings, proposals have been formulated to amend Articles 117, 123, and 131 of the Criminal Procedure Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan. These amendments are aimed at strengthening procedural guarantees, eliminating ambiguities in the interpretation of legal norms, ensuring greater consistency in investigative practice, and improving the overall effectiveness of criminal justice.

It is argued that the implementation of the proposed reforms would contribute to the further development of criminal procedural legislation, enhancement of legal certainty, protection of constitutional rights and freedoms, and strengthening of the rule of law within the criminal justice system of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

8. RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the results of the research, the following recommendations are proposed:

To amend Article 117 of the Criminal Procedure Code by establishing a clear legal framework governing the warning of close relatives who voluntarily agree to testify as witnesses or victims.

To introduce provisions regulating situations in which a person simultaneously acquires the procedural status of victim and suspect (or accused person) within the same criminal proceeding.

To exempt convicted or acquitted persons from warnings concerning criminal liability for refusing to testify or providing false testimony when questioned regarding separated criminal proceedings related to the same criminal act.

To amend Articles 123 and 131 of the Criminal Procedure Code by explicitly requiring that witnesses and victims participating in confrontation proceedings and identification procedures be warned of criminal liability for refusing to testify and for knowingly providing false testimony.

To develop unified methodological recommendations for investigators and inquiry officers concerning the application of procedural safeguards during investigative actions involving testimonial evidence.

To strengthen professional training programs aimed at improving investigators' knowledge and practical skills regarding crimes involving knowingly false testimony.

AUTHOR'S CONTRIBUTION

The author independently conducted the research, analyzed legislation and law enforcement practice, performed comparative legal analysis, formulated scientific conclusions, and developed legislative proposals presented in this article.

CONFLICT OF INTERES

The author declares no conflict of interest.

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REFERENCES

1. Kant, I. (n.d.). Philosophical works on law and society. Retrieved October 1, 2024, from <https://www.researchgate.net>

2. Mirziyoyev, S. M. (2024). Yurtning kuchi birlikda, qadri esa tinchlikdadir [Speech delivered at the celebration of the 33rd anniversary of Independence of the Republic of Uzbekistan]. Retrieved October 1, 2024, from <https://president.uz>
3. President of the Republic of Uzbekistan. (2016, October 21). Decree No. PF-4850 “On Measures for Further Reforming the Judicial and Legal System and Strengthening Guarantees for the Reliable Protection of Citizens’ Rights and Freedoms”. Retrieved October 1, 2024, from <https://lex.uz>
4. President of the Republic of Uzbekistan. (2017, November 30). Decree No. PF-5268 “On Additional Measures to Strengthen Guarantees of Citizens’ Rights and Freedoms in Judicial and Investigative Activities”. Retrieved October 1, 2024, from <https://lex.uz/docs/3432426>
5. President of the Republic of Uzbekistan. (2020, August 10). Decree No. PF-6041 “On Measures to Further Strengthen Guarantees for the Protection of Individual Rights and Freedoms in Judicial and Investigative Activities”. Retrieved October 1, 2024, from <https://lex.uz/docs/4939467>
6. President of the Republic of Uzbekistan. (2018, May 14). Resolution No. PQ-3723 “On Measures for the Radical Improvement of the System of Criminal and Criminal Procedural Legislation”. Retrieved October 1, 2024, from <https://lex.uz>
7. Murodov, B. B. (2018). Improvement of the Institution of Termination of Criminal Proceedings (Doctoral Dissertation). Academy of the Ministry of Internal Affairs, Tashkent.
8. Mirziyoyev, S. M. (2018). We Will Continue Our Path of National Development with Determination and Raise It to a New Stage. Tashkent: Uzbekistan Publishing House.
9. Mirziyoyev, S. M. Address to the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Retrieved October 1, 2024, from <https://xs.uz>
10. Mirziyoyev, S. M. (2017). The Constitution Is the Solid Foundation of Our Free and Prosperous Life and the Further Development of Our Country. Xalq So‘zi, December 7.
11. Rustambayev, M. H. (2021). Commentary on the Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Special Part (Vol. 3). Tashkent.
12. Republic of Uzbekistan. Criminal Procedure Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Retrieved from <https://lex.uz/docs/111460>
13. Republic of Uzbekistan. (2023). Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan (New Edition). Retrieved from <https://lex.uz/docs/6445145>
14. Russian Federation. (1993). Constitution of the Russian Federation. Retrieved from <http://www.constitution.ru>
15. United States of America. (1791). Constitution of the United States: Fifth Amendment. Retrieved from <https://constitutioncenter.org>
16. Republic of Uzbekistan. Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Retrieved from <https://lex.uz/docs/111453>
17. Republic of Uzbekistan. Law on Normative Legal Acts. Retrieved from <https://lex.uz>
18. Republic of Kazakhstan. (2014). Criminal Procedure Code of the Republic of Kazakhstan. Retrieved from <https://online.zakon.kz>
19. Turkmenistan. (2009). Criminal Procedure Code of Turkmenistan. Retrieved from <http://base.spininform.ru>